

Doctor's points of view on pharmacist's prescribing in Sweden

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Abstract:

Background:

As health care has advanced rapidly, pharmacist prescribing has spread globally, including countries like the United States, the United Kingdom, Switzerland, Canada, Australia, Poland, and Denmark (Mesbahi *et al.*, 2024). Pharmacist prescribing has many benefits, such as increased access to health care, better patient outcomes, and better use of pharmacists' skills and knowledge (Jebara *et al.*, 2018). Pharmacist prescribing can also solve the increasing problem of getting appointments with GPs (Piroux *et al.*, 2024).

In Sweden, pharmacists are not authorised to prescribe, renew, or amend prescriptions; instead, all such actions must be conducted through a doctor, a process that is both time-consuming and impractical. There is an ongoing debate about pharmacist's prescribing. Reports and several debate articles in Swedish medical magazines discussed the issue. Now, even politics has begun talking about the issue (Pettersson, 2025).

As doctors are the main partners to pharmacists in the health system, understanding their perspectives is crucial. So far, there has been no study that investigated their point of view on the issue in Sweden.

Aim:

The study aims to explore doctors' views on giving pharmacists the right to prescribe in Sweden.

Methods:

The study is a qualitative research study that involved in-depth, semi-structured interviews to gather and discuss doctors' perspectives on pharmacist supplements and independent prescribing in Sweden. 10 doctors with prescribing rights participated in the semi-structured interviews. Interviews were conducted using Microsoft Teams. The interviews were recorded and transcribed after consent from the participants. The semi-structured interview guide was based on current literature, validated and piloted. The interviews continued until saturation was achieved.

Setting:

All interviews with doctors were conducted using Microsoft Teams. The doctors were from different cities in Sweden. The doctors might be at home or in the office. All interviews were recorded and transcribed directly.

Key Findings:

There is general support for pharmacists' prescribing (PP) in Sweden. Nine out of ten doctors supported prescription renewal, and seven out of ten supported pharmacists' prescriptions for minor ailments, citing workload relief and utilising pharmacists' competencies. Less support for Pharmacist's Supplementary Prescribing (PSP) and Pharmacists' Independent Prescribing (PIP). There was a main concern from doctors about the pharmacist's ability to make clinical examinations.

Conclusion:

There is a possibility for (PP) in Sweden, especially prescription renewals and prescriptions for minor ailments. Opposing doctors were concerned about the education and training of pharmacists in clinical examination and the knowledge of the body as a whole. Doctors were less supportive of (PSP) and (PIP) because of this. Addressing this issue and other issues mentioned in the study could open the door for (PP) in Sweden.

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And last but not least, many thanks to all the doctors who participated in the study and were generous with their time. Thank you all.

List of abbreviations:

PSP - Pharmacist's Supplementary Prescribing

PIP - Pharmacist's Independent Prescribing

UTI - Urinary Tract Infection

RGU - Robert Gordon University

GCP – Good Clinical Practice

Introduction:

According to the Swedish National Board of Health and Welfare (Socialstyrelsen), only doctors, dentists, midwives, and certain nurses are authorised to prescribe in Sweden (Socialstyrelsen, 2021). Pharmacists have no authority to prescribe or modify a prescription. They cannot alter dosage forms or strengths of medicines; all changes must be made by a doctor, which is a time-consuming and impractical process.

Some reports and debate articles have discussed the benefits of granting pharmacists the right to prescribe and utilising their competencies. Pharmacists (Boström, 2022; Kidd, 2022; Olofsson, 2019) have all written articles that pharmacists should be given the right to renew expired prescriptions for long-term use medicines, as is the case in Denmark. Mikael Hoffman, a doctor and the head of the foundation NEPI - a network for pharmaceutical epidemiology and Chairman of the Swedish Medical Association's committee for pharmaceutical issues_ also wrote in a debate article about giving pharmacists the right to renew prescriptions to save efforts. He also called for better cooperation between doctors and pharmacists (Hoffman, 2023). All these writers have advocated for only a partial right to prescribe.

A graduation project at Linnaeus University in Sweden also investigated the temporary legislation that granted pharmacists an exception to adjust the strengths of Levaxin tablets due to shortages. This study, however, also discussed only a partial right to prescribe, which was granted for a brief period. The study concluded that both pharmacists and patients benefited from the temporary change in the legislation (Satingin Matsanders 2018)

Two pilot studies at Uppsala University in Sweden investigated a broader scope of pharmacist prescribing and its benefits. The benefits of pharmacist prescribing include better access to health care, increased healthcare system capacity, and increased job satisfaction for pharmacists (Royal Pharmaceutical Society of Great Britain, 2024). The studies examined the perspectives of pharmacists and clinical pharmacists on supplementary and independent prescribing, drawing on examples from countries such as the UK, Poland, New Zealand, the USA, and Canada. The study that investigated the pharmacist's point of view concluded that there was mixed support for pharmacists obtaining prescribing rights, identifying the main barrier as opposition from other healthcare workers (Murad, 2022). The clinical pharmacist's study concluded that most clinical pharmacists supported gaining the right to prescribe, but only in collaboration with doctors and other healthcare professionals (Alsaadi, 2022).

According to Sandra Murad, the study's weaknesses included the low number of participants and the fact that the interview was not pilot tested before conducting the study, which would have allowed for improvements to the questions (Murad, 2022). When it comes to the weaknesses of Rusul Alsaadi's study she also stated that the response rate was low about 23%, not everybody answered the open questions in the survey as they were not obligatory, some of the open questions were not that clear as one can see in the answers there were some misunderstandings

and finally the IT system used for the survey did not allow the participants to save their answers and complete in another time, it had to be done all in one sitting (Alsaadi, 2022).

To summarise, pharmacists in Sweden do not have the authority to prescribe or amend prescriptions. However, there has been some debate, in the form of articles and recent studies, advocating for pharmacists to be granted the right to prescribe. All studies mentioned have shown some positive attitude towards giving pharmacists the right to prescribe; however, these studies have only considered the pharmacist's point of view. No study has been conducted exploring doctors' perspectives on pharmacists' prescribing in Sweden. It's all in the studies and debate level within the healthcare sector. There is no current policy initiative to introduce pharmacist's prescribing in Sweden, but recently, an MP from the biggest opposition party, the Swedish Social Party, made a statement about giving pharmacists the right to prescribe (Pettersson, 2025), which sparked a new wave of debate.

Research Aim, Question and Objectives:

Research Aim:

The study aims to explore doctors' views on giving pharmacists the right to prescribe in Sweden. What are the facilitators, barriers, and concerns?

Research Question:

What are doctor's views on pharmacists getting the right to prescribe in Sweden?

Research Objectives:

- To explore doctors' views on pharmacists' independent prescribing, supplement prescribing, renewing prescriptions for chronic diseases and prescribing medicines for minor ailments.
- To assess the doctor's acceptance of pharmacists prescribing medicines.
- To investigate doctors' views on the positive effect of pharmacist's prescribing on reducing the workload on GPs and clinics.
- To evaluate doctors' views on utilising pharmacies' availability and extended opening hours, even on weekends, to help renew prescriptions and obtain prescription medicines for minor ailments.

Methods:

Study Design:

The study is a qualitative research study that involves in-depth, semi-structured interviews to gather and discuss doctors' perspectives on pharmacist supplements and independent prescribing in Sweden.

Methodology:

Phase One:

Literature review: This involves searching Google, Google Scholar, and the RGU library search, which links to databases such as PubMed and MEDLINE, as well as the Uppsala University library search, which links to Swedish databases like Diva, to search for studies and articles on pharmacist prescribing in Sweden, with a particular focus on studies examining doctors' views on pharmacists' prescribing practices.

Phase two:

Contacting doctors and conducting and recording the semi-structured interviews.

Phase Three:

Analysing the collected data and writing the final report.

Research Setting:

All interviews with doctors were conducted using Microsoft Teams; the doctors were at home or the office. The doctors were from different cities in Sweden. The advantage of using Microsoft Teams is that participants in the interview can see each other, which leads to better communication, as one can identify misunderstandings and observe facial expressions. Additionally, all interviews were transcribed directly.

Participants:

10 doctors with prescribing rights participated in the semi-structured interviews. Where thematic saturation was reached.

Recruitment:

Doctors who have prescribing rights known to the student through personal networks were contacted to participate in the study. After agreeing to participate, participants were asked to sign a consent form that explained their rights to them.

Sampling:

The sampling is considered a mix of purposive sampling, in which doctors with prescribing rights are intentionally selected, and snowball sampling, in which doctors are already suggesting other doctors to participate in the study.

10 doctors were interviewed, which is considered enough to reach thematic saturation. Otherwise, two more interviews will be conducted if saturation is not reached; another two interviews will be conducted, and so on until saturation is reached. (Guest, Bunce and Johnson, 2006)- Thematic saturation was reached by 10 doctors in this study.

Inclusion and exclusion criteria:

The study concerns the views of only doctors with prescribing rights and does not include the opinions of other health professionals with prescribing rights.

Inclusion criteria:

- Doctors with the right to prescribe in Sweden from different settings (GPs and specialists)

Exclusion criteria:

- Dentists with prescribing rights in Sweden
- Midwives with prescribing rights in Sweden
- Nurses with prescription rights in Sweden.

Development of data collection/generation tools:

The study was first piloted on one doctor to check that everything worked well. That helped improve the questions, interview technique, practical issues like using Microsoft Teams, and the time needed to conduct an interview, which turned out to be much less than the estimated time of 1 hour.

To ensure the trustworthiness and reliability of this qualitative study, the four pillars of trustworthiness were implemented.

1. **Credibility:** To ensure that the findings accurately reflect the doctor's perspectives, member checks are employed. All participating doctors will be asked to review the transcripts and the study's findings.
2. **Transferability:** To help others decide if the findings are relevant, detailed information and descriptions are provided about all the steps of the study, including data collection, sampling of participating doctors, and data analysis.
3. **Dependability:** To ensure consistency and stability, all steps were thoroughly documented, including the process of conducting interviews with the doctors, the interview questions used, and the data analysis process. Also, the supervisor will be involved in all the study steps to ensure transparency.
4. **Confirmability:** To ensure that there is no bias, all steps were thoroughly documented, including the process of drawing conclusions. Additionally, the supervisor will serve as an external reviewer to verify that the findings are based on data and not influenced by bias. (Jansen, 2025).

Method of data collection:

Data collection process:

Data were collected from semi-structured interviews with 10 doctors.

The questions were open-ended, allowing participants to elaborate without using judgmental or value-laden language.

A demographic table is produced with information on the doctor's sex, age, years of experience, and level of education.

The interviews began by ensuring that the participant understood the purpose of the study, its objectives, how the data would be managed, and the expected duration of the interview.

The participants were asked to sign a consent form that informed them about their right to withdraw from the study at any time or to change or delete their statements. Future contact details were provided if anyone has questions about the survey. The interview commenced after the participant had given their consent. (Austin and Sutton, 2019).

Data collection tools:

All interviews were recorded and transcribed using Microsoft Teams. Then, the transcriptions were stripped of any identifying information, such as names and locations.

To maintain anonymity, a coding list for the participating doctors was made. Each doctor was assigned a number, and each recorded interview was corresponded to a specific doctor; only the doctor's number is mentioned in the discussion of the results. For example, as participants, "P3 thinks..." or "P6 said" All interviews will be conducted via Microsoft Teams and will be automatically uploaded to RGU's OneDrive.

Data analysis:

The transcribed interviews were analysed and stored at RGU's OneDrive. The transcribed data from the recorded sessions were then analysed using coding and theming to summarise the findings of the interviews. In coding, similar issues and topics narrated by the participants, i.e., their thoughts and feelings, were identified and grouped. This was done both manually, by writing on the margins and highlighting the transcripts, and by using NVivo software. In Theming, similar codes were drawn together coherently and meaningfully to form headings for sections in the study's findings. This was done manually and by NVivo software (Austin and Sutton, 2019). Everything was anonymised and presented from the participants' points of view. Themes, codes, and quotations from participants were analysed to provide an in-depth view of the doctors' feelings and thoughts.

Data storage:

Data storage and destruction will follow RGU's research governance policies. The recorded interviews will be uploaded to RGU's OneDrive as soon as possible after the interview.

Ethics approval:

The final project proposal was reviewed and approved by the School of Pharmacy and Life Sciences Ethics Committee at Robert Gordon University. All data collected will be confidential and anonymised, and consent forms will be signed before participation in the study. Participants have the right to withdraw from the study at any time and to review what they said during the study process and after publication. Participants were also provided with information on where to turn if they have any concerns regarding the study in the future.

All study materials will be stored, processed, and destroyed in accordance with pharmacy and life sciences standard operating procedures, which reference Robert Gordon University's research governance policies. The research will adhere to all relevant Robert Gordon University policies, including Research Governance and Research Ethics. All research team members have completed the Good Clinical Practice (GCP) for Research training.

Results:

Participants Characteristics:

In total, 10 doctors from different regions in Sweden were interviewed, comprising 6 males and 4 females, with varying specialities, ages, and years of experience. As shown in Table 1.

Participants	Age	Speciality	Gender	Years of experience
P1	50-60	Surgery and GP	Male	27
P2	30-40	GP specialist (almost finished)	Male	5
P3	50-60	Paediatrics	Male	33
P4	50-60	GP Specialist	Female	15
P5	60-70	GP Specialist	Female	38
P6	40-50	Internal Medicine	Male	15
P7	60-70	Internal Medicine and Clinical Pharmacology	Female	36
P8	30-40	Psychiatry	Female	8
P9	40-50	Internal Medicine and Cardiology	Male	17
P10	50-60	Internal Medicine and Endocrinology	Male	33

Table 1.

Qualitative Data:

The doctors were asked to give their views on 4 different possible prescribing models in Sweden.

- Pharmacist's supplementary prescribing.
- Pharmacist's Independent prescribing.
- Pharmacist's prescribing for minor ailments.
- Pharmacist's prescription renewal.

The views of doctors on these prescribing models were classified into 2 themes: those for and against prescribing, which are represented generally in Table 2.

Participants	Pharmacist's supplementary prescription	Pharmacist's Independent prescribing.	Pharmacists' prescribing for minor ailments.	Pharmacist's prescription renewal.
P1	Against	Against	Against	For
P2	For	For	For	For
P3	For	For	For	For
P4	For	For	For	For
P5	Against	Against	Against	Against
P6	For	For	For	For
P7	Against	Against	Against	For (with access to the patient's journal)
P8	For	Against	For	For
P9	For	For	For	For
P10	Against	Against	For	For

Table2.

The study resulted in 2 themes, and 9 subthemes parented table 3.

Themes	Subthemes
For	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other health care professionals already practice this. • Further, specialised training and medical record access for pharmacists. • Reduces the workload on doctors. • Make use of Pharmacist's competence.
Against	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lacking clinical experience and training. • Inability to make differential diagnosis. • Patient's Health safety issues. • Unnecessary in Sweden. • It is a doctor's role.

Table 3.

For:

- Other health care professionals already practice this:

When doctors were asked about their views on Pharmacist supplementary prescribing (PSP) and independent pharmacist prescribing (PIP) many doctors were positive to these prescribing models referring to that nurses at clinics in Sweden are now following up, assessing and adjusting doses and adding the ability to pharmacists to prescribe would be great, nevertheless pharmacists are experts in medicines and have gone extensive 5 years education programmes as a base education.

“Yes, I think it sounds good, and it would work. We have a similar model, I would say, in the cardiac clinic, for example. There is a specialised heart failure nurse who follows up patients, takes the necessary tests, and they have the right to adjust heart failure medications depending on the findings, with feedback to the doctor.” P9

“I would rather see a pharmacist working in many clinics than a nurse, a pharmacist with five years of education, academic and who knows drug interactions, just give that person clinical experience and they will learn it quickly”, P6

- Further, specialised training and medical records access for pharmacists:

The importance of further training has been highlighted by many doctors in the study to minimise mistakes. It has been mentioned when asked about (PSP) that nurses at cardiology clinics take care of about 80% of patients. Nurses feel confident in assessing patients, follow-ups, and adjusting doses. If pharmacists get the right training, they should be as confident as they are.

“The nurses feel confident, and so should pharmacists if they receive such training. Being able to do so wouldn’t be unusual, but as I mentioned, it places quite high demands on the pharmacists.” P2

Other doctors have emphasised the importance of building clinical experience, which can be achieved through regular meetings with patients in the same clinic and field of expertise, rather than in a pharmacy setting where patient clinical interactions are less frequent.

“The clinical skills will be gained because when you meet such patients at such a clinic all the time, you get that exposure, and that’s how you learn it”, P6

“But if you get the right education and such”, P8

“Specific area of practice, and if they constantly see the same patient, and maybe it gets easier for them after each time”, P8

The above quotes from P8 are talking about clinical experience.

P2 and P7 both emphasised the importance of access to patients' medical records for obtaining a comprehensive understanding of whether a patient has a disease or is undergoing a treatment. They raised the concern that this is not possible now at pharmacies if someone wants to prescribe a medicine for minor ailments or a prescription renewal-

"What I think is that for regulatory reasons, it may be difficult for a pharmacy, perhaps, to take part in all the collective medical records that exist within healthcare and so on, so I don't know a lot of things about the patient's other diseases that are not apparent at the pharmacy" P2

"No, exactly no, under those conditions, if the pharmacist can see in the medical record, then I can see that such a service would be a help for the healthcare system", P7

P7 speaking about prescription renewals.

- Reduces the workload on doctors:

This is one of the most important advantages that emerged in the study when doctors were asked about their views on pharmacists' prescribing. Almost all doctors who support pharmacist prescription (PP) cited this as the main advantage.

"That patients don't have to burden doctors. Doctors can save time for the more complicated cases," P3

"Yes, yes, but it will certainly relieve, so you don't need to call the GP if you have a slight cold with a cough and need a little stronger cough medicine, or a woman who has repeated urinary tract infections doesn't need to call the GP and get an emergency appointment after two or three days" P10

"But as I said, it would be very relieving for clinics", P4

- Make use of Pharmacist's competence:

In Sweden, pharmacists have a very limited scope. Pharmacists are not allowed to make any changes to prescriptions (dosage form, strength). Pharmacists do not do any real medical assessments. This issue has been brought forward by P6.

"For example, if you ask me? I think it's a waste of the pharmacist's competence to come to you for skin care advice and product recommendations. Yes, it's good that you can get sun protection factor cream, which ones and how to use them to prevent problems. But should the pharmacist who has this advanced competence really deal with cosmetic skin care advice? Ideally, they should actually deal with qualified medical assessments," P6

Against:

- Lacking clinical experience and training:

Many doctors who opposed (PP) argued that pharmacists lack the necessary clinical education and experience, and that pharmacy education has traditionally focused on other areas rather than clinical skills and diagnosis. Other doctors' concerns regarding this issue as that pharmacists do not have the full knowledge of the body like doctors, which can have a great effect when making clinical assessments and diagnoses.

"It's not just about a strong symptom. It can go very bad as well as wrong if you don't have knowledge of the whole body." P5

"Different education from the beginning and different competences, so that. If there are no doctors or nurses, then you may have to look for other temporary solutions." P7

"It's not healthcare education. Pharmacists' education mainly covers treatment aspects and other related topics, not including clinical examination techniques and the necessary assessments during patient examinations. However, I don't think it's a good suggestion." P7

Also, when asked about their views on (PP) in Sweden, many doctors thought that nurses have much better knowledge and training when it came to clinical expertise, as they have direct contact with patients.

"The district nurse can clinically examine patients closely. She has taken a course, knows when something is wrong and can come back to me if she doesn't know what to do" P1

"In that case, I think it is better to have, for example, a nurse. A nurse would be happy to follow up, yes, a specialist nurse who may be part of the same team as the doctor," P7.

- Inability to make differential diagnosis:

This is also an issue that has been raised by doctors when interviewed. The ability to differentiate between different diseases. This issue typically occurs, according to these doctors, when pharmacists are making (PIP) or prescribing for minor ailments that require a diagnosis.

"But sometimes the patient may present with symptoms that make you have to think in completely different ways as a doctor, differentially diagnose. That what the patient is saying actually has nothing to do with the current disease at all, but you may have thoughts that it is about some other disease process that is going on in parallel, especially in rheumatology." P7

P1 spoke about two very common infections, urinary tract infections (UTIs) and tonsillitis.

"And yes, take a urine dipstick, and there are infections there. But is it cystitis, or is it pyelonephritis? It becomes a little difficult to determine for him, the pharmacist, and for us

sometimes. It becomes like this, where you supplement with, for example, a neutrophil supplement or with a urine culture, so it will take a lot of time. Little things sometimes can be huge. I mean, I can come with a sore throat. Yes, I have a sore throat, fever, and difficulty swallowing, and ultimately it could be an abscess.” P1

- Patient’s Health safety issues:

Doctors have stated that (PP) can lead to problems in patients' health safety issues. P8 said that even if a pharmacist received specific clinical advanced training, it is not broad enough, which can jeopardise patients' health safety.

“I think that even if you have been trained in that area, you might not gain this broader knowledge. In this example with the lungs, you don't get a differential diagnosis. Maybe it's something with the heart? Is it something gynaecological after all? Is it something else? It feels like it could be easy to miss things It feels risky and a little more uncertain.” P8

According to P7, simply following guidelines to prescribe can lead to patient health safety issues for pharmacists. Like prescribing nitrofurantoin for a UTI. The pharmacist should look at the kidney filtration rate first, as it can be toxic. Nitrofurantoin is primarily renally excreted.

“Treatment according to guidelines like this, but you may also need to know if the patient for nitrofurantoin has a kidney filtration that makes it an effective treatment and so what limits there are and that it is safe and so on, and then you have to look at the lab results and then it becomes more complex already you also need to consider that it may sound like a typical urinary tract infection with frequent urine urges and so on. But it may be a patient who has a different urine urgency problem.” P7

- Unnecessary in Sweden

Another aspect that was mentioned by opposing doctors is that (PP) is unnecessary in Sweden. P5 noted that doctors and nurses work very closely in Sweden, with specialised nurses doing a lot of work; there is simply no place for pharmacists.

“We have district nurses who are specialist nurses who are trained to handle the simpler cases. They also have the right to prescribe certain medicines, which is why I think it's just going to be cake on cake.” P5

P7 stated that if pharmacists wish to work clinically, a shorter course should be available for them to become doctors.

- It is a doctor's role

This is merely a doctor’s role when it comes to following up with patients, diagnosing, and prescribing medicines. P7 stated that doctors are obliged to follow up their patients, and P10 said

“This is a 100% doctor's role”, P10, when asked about his view on (PIP)

Discussion:

The aim of this study was to explore doctors' views on four models of (PP). The four models are (PSP), (PIP), Pharmacist prescription for minor ailments and Pharmacist prescription renewal.

Ten doctors who were interviewed were, in general, positive about (PP). Nearly all doctors supported prescription renewal by pharmacists—nine out of ten. A significant number also had positive views about prescriptions for minor ailments—seven out of ten. (PSP), (PIP), there were some doctors who supported — (Table 2).

The main reasons for their positive views are that (PP) reduces the workload on doctors, provides more space to focus on more complicated cases, and utilises pharmacists' competencies more effectively.

The rest, who opposed (PP) in one or all its forms, have raised valid points that could be discussed in future studies. Such points include the lack of clinical expertise to diagnose, (PP) is unnecessary in Sweden, as the Swedish healthcare system is organised differently, and follow-up and prescribing are solely the rights of a doctor.

However, all doctors interviewed expressed concerns about the clinical experience and training of pharmacists. Some felt reassured upon learning that mainly (PSP) and (PIP) would be working in clinics and hospitals equipped with all necessary facilities and staffed with other healthcare professionals, and that there would be extensive advanced clinical training in specific healthcare areas. Others remained unconvinced and raised the aforementioned issues earlier.

The study's findings suggest that (PP) in Sweden is possible, especially for prescription renewals and prescribing for minor ailments. There is. The concerns raised against (PSP) and (PIP) should be addressed before granting pharmacists the authority to prescribe in Sweden. This could be achieved through future studies that compare practices in countries like the UK, which have already implemented PSP and PIP.

Future Work:

This study could be considered as a completion of (Murad 2022) and (Alsaadi 2022), which investigated the views of pharmacists and clinical pharmacists on (PP) in Sweden. What is needed in the future is the views of patients on (PP) in Sweden to get a complete picture. This study, along with the previous studies mentioned and the suggested future studies, will help determine the future of (PP) in Sweden, and also the politician's involvement and opinion play a vital role.

Study Strengths and Limitations:

This study, to the best of my knowledge, is the first in Sweden to examine (PP) from the doctor's perspective. This qualitative study, conducted through interviews, provides an in-depth examination of what doctors really think about (PP) in Sweden. The interviews provided an opportunity to delve into details not possible with a quantitative study.

Among the study's limitations is that it is a small study that involved only the views of 10 doctors. The results of the study cannot be generalised; it only applies to Sweden. Word count for the study is limited to 4500 words only, which affects the analysis and discussion.

Conclusion:

The study explored doctors' views on (PP) in Sweden on various aspects. Generally, the doctors were positive, with general acceptance. However, some have opposed (PIP) and (PSP), while many others have supported the prescription of minor ailments and prescription renewals.

The doctors identified reducing the workload and utilising the pharmacies' extended hours, including weekends, as well as making use of the pharmacist's expertise, as key advantages.

The fact that pharmacists will undergo further education and clinical training before becoming prescribers has reassured a major concern among doctors in the study, specifically regarding how pharmacists will conduct clinical examinations.

Furthermore, studies are needed to see if pharmacist's prescriptions will become a reality in Sweden. The patients' and politicians' views are next.

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Appendix:

- List of Tables:

Table 1, Participants Characteristics

Participants	Age	Speciality	Gender	Years of experience
P1	50-60	Surgery and GP	Male	27
P2	30-40	GP specialist (almost finished)	Male	5
P3	50-60	Paediatrics	Male	19
P4	50-60	GP Specialist	Female	15
P5	60-70	GP Specialist	Female	38
P6	40-50	Internal Medicine	Male	15
P7	60-70	Internal Medicine and Clinical Pharmacology	Female	36
P8	30-40	Psychiatry	Female	8
P9	40-50	Internal Medicine and Cardiology	Male	17
P10	50-60	Internal Medicine and Endocrinology	Male	33

Table 2. Participants Views

Participants	Pharmacist's supplementary prescription	Pharmacist's Independent prescribing.	Pharmacists' prescribing for minor ailments.	Pharmacist's prescription renewal.
P1	Against	Against	Against	For
P2	For	For	For	For
P3	For	For	For	For
P4	For	For	For	For
P5	Against	Against	Against	Against
P6	For	For	For	For
P7	Against	Against	Against	For (with access to the patient's journal)
P8	For	Against	For	For
P9	For	For	For	For
P10	Against	Against	For	For

Table 3. Themes and Subthemes

Themes	Subthemes
For	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other health care professionals already practice this. • Further, specialised training and medical record access for pharmacists. • Reduces the workload on doctors. • Make use of Pharmacist's competence.
Against	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lacking clinical experience and training. • Inability to make differential diagnosis. • Patient's Health safety issues. • Unnecessary in Sweden. • It is a doctor's role.

Interview Schedule

The interview will begin with an icebreaker, during which the doctor will be asked to share a little about themselves, including their age and years of experience.

The interview questions will cover four key aspects, each accompanied by a definition of the model and a clear example.

The four aspects are:

- Supplementary pharmacist prescribing.
- Independent pharmacist prescribing.
- Pharmacist prescribing for minor illnesses.
- Pharmacist's right to renew prescriptions.

Pharmacists will prescribe after they have undergone further training in a specific area of practice known as the scope of practice.

Interview Questions

- Tell us a bit about yourself

Prompts:

Your age

years of experience

Speciality

- Supplementary prescribing:

It is a voluntary partnership between a doctor and a pharmacist to implement an agreed patient-specific Clinical management plan (CMP).

The doctor makes the diagnosis and develops the CMP. The pharmacist has the authority to prescribe, adjust doses, and order lab tests as outlined in the CMP, depending on the patient's progress. This requires close communication among the pharmacist, the doctor, and the patient.

Example:

Hospital outpatient clinic

Condition: Rheumatoid arthritis

A rheumatologist diagnoses a patient with rheumatoid arthritis. The rheumatologist develops a Clinical Management Plan (CMP) that outlines the patient's treatment goals, medications to be used (e.g., methotrexate, NSAIDs), dose adjustments, and monitoring requirements.

A supplementary prescribing pharmacist then works with the patient in follow-up clinics, reviewing symptoms, adjusting methotrexate dosage within the CMP, ordering blood tests, and providing advice on side effects and lifestyle, all without requiring the doctor to see the patient each time.

The pharmacist doesn't diagnose or initiate treatment but can manage care under the agreed CMP.

- What do you think of this model of prescribing, which utilises pharmacists' competencies and reduces the workload on the healthcare system in general?
- What do you think are the advantages and disadvantages of this model?

- Independent prescribing:

It is a clinical authority granted to a qualified pharmacist after further training in a specific area of practice. The pharmacist is authorised to assess patients, diagnose conditions, make clinical decisions, and initiate, adjust, or discontinue medications without supervision from another healthcare professional, such as a doctor. They are required to adhere to evidence-based medicine and national and local guidelines when making clinical decisions.

Example:

An independent pharmacist prescriber assesses a patient presenting with respiratory symptoms. After taking a detailed history and performing spirometry, the pharmacist diagnoses asthma. The clinical pharmacist initiates treatment by prescribing an inhaled corticosteroid, which may be combined with a long-acting beta-agonist if indicated and provides a personalised asthma action plan. The pharmacist also offers training on the proper use of inhaler techniques. The pharmacist independently monitors the patient's symptoms and lung function, adjusting treatment regimens based on clinical guidelines and patient feedback, while ensuring that any emerging issues are referred to a specialist if necessary.

In every independent prescribing situation, the pharmacist utilises their clinical expertise to manage the patient's care from start to finish. This approach necessitates comprehensive training, adherence to evidence-based guidelines, and effective communication with patients to ensure safe and effective treatment.

This also requires close communication among the pharmacist, patient, and other healthcare professionals as needed.

- What do you think of this model of prescribing, which utilises pharmacists' competencies and reduces the workload on the healthcare system?
- What do you think are the advantages and disadvantages of this model?

- Minor ailments prescribing:

According to the Ontario College of Pharmacists, minor ailments are health conditions that

- Can be managed with minimal treatment or self-care.
- Requiring no lab tests.
- Have a low risk that the treatment will mask an underlying serious condition.
- No red flags in medical history that suggest a more serious condition.
- Minimal or short-term follow-up is required.

It is a form of independent prescribing where the pharmacist usually carries out directly at the pharmacy. The pharmacist must have undergone further training to assess the patient, read their medical history, and make a diagnosis.

Some minor ailments examples include oral thrush (candidal stomatitis), conjunctivitis (allergic, bacterial, and viral), Dermatitis (eczema, allergic, atopic, and contact), Nausea and vomiting of pregnancy, and urinary tract infections (uncomplicated).

Example:

Community pharmacy

Condition: Uncomplicated urinary tract infection (UTI)

A woman presents to a pharmacist with symptoms of a urinary tract infection (UTI). The independent prescribing pharmacist takes a clinical history, assesses symptoms, rules out red flags, and diagnoses an uncomplicated UTI. The pharmacist then prescribes nitrofurantoin, offers self-care advice, and explains when to seek further help.

The pharmacist enters the encounter into a shared patient record system (if available) but does not need a doctor's approval to prescribe.

- What do you think of this model of prescribing, which utilises pharmacists' competencies and reduces the workload on the healthcare system?
- What do you think are the advantages and disadvantages of this model?

- Pharmacist's prescription renewal:

It empowers pharmacists to renew prescriptions for chronic conditions, including diabetes, hypertension, anticoagulants, and cholesterol medications, among others. This approach mirrors the system in Denmark, where pharmacists can renew prescriptions for a single refill and the smallest available pack size. This is beneficial to all patients, especially the elderly.

Example:

On Friday evening, an elderly man goes to the pharmacy to request his Eliquis, an anticoagulant medication. The pharmacist informs him that there are no refills available on his prescription. Since the elderly man is not familiar with the internet, he cannot renew his prescription online or through an online doctor. Obtaining an appointment with a doctor is challenging, often taking up to five days to renew a prescription after contacting the general practitioner (GP). The earliest he can obtain a refill is on Monday; this fast track is not typically available to everyone.

The pharmacist renews the Eliquis prescription on the spot with one refill, pending the patient's appointment with his GP.

- What do you think of this model of prescribing, which utilises pharmacists' competencies and reduces the workload on the healthcare system?
- What do you think are the advantages and disadvantages of this model?